

Manganese-doped zinc oxide quantum dots improve boar sperm quality via antioxidant and antibacterial activities during liquid storage

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Supplementary File

Table S1

Effects of different concentrations of Mn-ZnO on sperm motility and other movement parameters in boars.

Kinematic variables	Time (d)	Groups			
		0 µg/mL Mn-ZnO	2.5 µg/mL Mn-ZnO	5 µg/mL Mn-ZnO	10 µg/mL Mn-ZnO
Motility (%)	1	80.19±0.58 ^a	80.08±0.83 ^a	81.13±0.82 ^a	76.28±1.44 ^b
	2	71.90±0.68 ^a	69.79±0.84 ^a	72.17±0.64 ^a	69.81±0.84 ^a
	3	66.27±0.76 ^a	67.28±1.08 ^a	69.49±0.62 ^a	67.17±0.80 ^a
	4	64.38±0.63 ^b	65.39±0.60 ^{ab}	68.50±0.73 ^a	67.13±0.81 ^{ab}
	5	57.96±1.36 ^a	59.68±1.36 ^a	61.59±1.26 ^a	53.34±0.81 ^b
VCL (µm/s)	1	103.19±3.16 ^a	102.76±4.52 ^a	101.57±2.13 ^a	86.87±3.87 ^b
	2	76.20±1.94 ^a	74.47±1.97 ^a	83.30±1.77 ^a	75.98±2.71 ^a
	3	65.87±1.61 ^b	68.08±2.81 ^{ab}	76.25±1.79 ^a	70.30±1.37 ^{ab}
	4	52.99±0.93 ^b	67.29±1.44 ^a	70.45±2.69 ^a	61.40±2.54 ^{ab}
	5	52.38±1.93 ^a	51.92±2.52 ^a	48.18±1.49 ^a	45.16±2.14 ^a
VSL (µm/s)	1	28.96±0.80 ^a	27.94±1.17 ^a	28.09±0.87 ^a	26.16±1.68 ^a
	2	22.20±0.60 ^a	21.53±0.74 ^a	23.54±0.57 ^a	20.70±0.77 ^a
	3	18.45±0.63 ^b	18.49±0.56 ^b	22.20±0.59 ^a	21.07±0.50 ^{ab}
	4	15.32±0.39 ^b	19.60±0.37 ^a	19.58±0.51 ^a	18.37±0.59 ^a
	5	14.68±0.61 ^a	14.43±1.32 ^a	14.55±0.58 ^a	12.50±1.01 ^a
VAP (µm/s)	1	43.79±1.07 ^{ab}	43.87±1.59 ^{ab}	44.63±1.02 ^a	40.45±2.03 ^b
	2	36.73±0.63 ^a	34.90±0.79 ^a	37.58±0.78 ^a	33.80±1.03 ^a
	3	30.91±0.68 ^b	30.66±0.62 ^b	36.08±0.71 ^a	33.02±0.54 ^{ab}
	4	26.65±0.69 ^b	31.06±0.99 ^a	31.65±0.48 ^a	29.03±0.92 ^{ab}
	5	24.26±0.95 ^a	22.53±1.99 ^{ab}	23.33±0.91 ^{ab}	20.20±1.52 ^b
BCF (Hz)	1	8.77±0.11 ^a	9.07±0.18 ^a	8.95±0.14 ^a	8.64±0.32 ^a
	2	7.05±0.27 ^{ab}	6.81±0.10 ^b	7.47±0.11 ^a	7.31±0.17 ^{ab}
	3	5.79±0.14 ^b	6.08±0.11 ^{ab}	6.55±0.16 ^a	6.23±0.15 ^{ab}
	4	5.50±0.07 ^b	5.83±0.13 ^{ab}	6.32±0.16 ^a	6.07±0.13 ^{ab}
	5	5.29±0.16 ^b	5.86±0.09 ^{ab}	6.12±0.18 ^a	5.63±0.21 ^{ab}
ALH (µm)	1	1.31±0.03 ^a	1.38±0.04 ^a	1.34±0.02 ^a	1.20±0.04 ^b
	2	1.10±0.01 ^{ab}	1.01±0.02 ^{bc}	1.12±0.02 ^a	0.98±0.02 ^c
	3	0.88±0.02 ^b	0.86±0.02 ^b	0.98±0.01 ^a	0.94±0.01 ^{ab}
	4	0.77±0.01 ^b	0.89±0.01 ^a	0.91±0.02 ^a	0.87±0.03 ^a
	5	0.71±0.02 ^a	0.69±0.04 ^a	0.71±0.02 ^a	0.59±0.04 ^b
STR (%)	1	0.64±0.01 ^a	0.64±0.01 ^a	0.63±0.01 ^a	0.65±0.01 ^a
	2	0.60±0.01 ^a	0.62±0.01 ^a	0.63±0.01 ^a	0.61±0.01 ^a
	3	0.58±0.01 ^b	0.60±0.01 ^{ab}	0.62±0.01 ^a	0.60±0.00 ^{ab}
	4	0.55±0.01 ^b	0.61±0.01 ^a	0.60±0.01 ^a	0.58±0.01 ^{ab}
	5	0.54±0.02 ^b	0.63±0.01 ^a	0.63±0.01 ^a	0.60±0.01 ^a
LIN (%)	1	0.29±0.00 ^a	0.27±0.01 ^a	0.28±0.01 ^a	0.30±0.01 ^a
	2	0.28±0.00 ^a	0.29±0.00 ^a	0.29±0.01 ^a	0.30±0.01 ^a
	3	0.29±0.00 ^a	0.30±0.00 ^a	0.30±0.00 ^a	0.30±0.00 ^a
	4	0.29±0.01 ^a	0.31±0.01 ^a	0.30±0.01 ^a	0.30±0.00 ^a
	5	0.27±0.01 ^a	0.28±0.01 ^a	0.28±0.01 ^a	0.25±0.02 ^a
WOB (%)	1	0.45±0.00 ^{ab}	0.43±0.00 ^b	0.44±0.00 ^{ab}	0.47±0.01 ^a
	2	0.48±0.01 ^a	0.48±0.00 ^a	0.46±0.00 ^a	0.47±0.01 ^a
	3	0.49±0.00 ^a	0.48±0.00 ^a	0.47±0.00 ^a	0.48±0.00 ^a
	4	0.49±0.01 ^a	0.48±0.00 ^a	0.48±0.00 ^a	0.44±0.02 ^b
	5	0.47±0.01 ^a	0.43±0.01 ^{bc}	0.44±0.01 ^{ab}	0.40±0.02 ^c

Table S2

Effects of different concentrations of ZnO on sperm motility and other movement parameters in boars.

Kinematic variables	Time (d)	Groups			
		0 µg/mL ZnO	0.5 µg/mL ZnO	1 µg/mL ZnO	2 µg/mL ZnO
Motility (%)	1	80.19±0.58 ^a	80.43±0.76 ^a	81.17±1.21 ^a	75.48±1.57 ^b
	2	71.90±0.68 ^{ab}	69.24±0.70 ^b	72.62±0.88 ^a	71.58±0.80 ^{ab}
	3	66.27±0.76 ^b	67.37±0.84 ^{ab}	69.86±0.76 ^a	68.34±0.85 ^{ab}
	4	64.38±0.63 ^b	65.50±1.01 ^{ab}	68.50±0.81 ^a	67.67±0.61 ^{ab}
	5	57.96±1.36 ^b	60.28±0.58 ^{ab}	63.08±0.87 ^a	58.24±0.96 ^b
VCL (µm/s)	1	103.19±3.16 ^a	103.85±3.83 ^a	98.06±3.27 ^a	89.35±5.03 ^b
	2	76.20±1.94 ^a	74.76±1.65 ^a	82.22±1.53 ^a	80.20±2.70 ^a
	3	65.87±1.61 ^a	69.19±1.67 ^a	68.68±1.18 ^a	64.36±2.59 ^a
	4	52.99±0.93 ^b	55.67±2.00 ^{ab}	62.98±1.09 ^a	61.94±1.30 ^a
	5	52.38±1.93 ^a	54.39±1.61 ^a	60.05±1.47 ^a	55.68±2.20 ^a
VSL (µm/s)	1	28.96±0.80 ^a	28.92±1.28 ^a	29.23±1.14 ^a	25.13±1.42 ^b
	2	22.20±0.60 ^a	22.50±0.44 ^a	22.63±0.98 ^a	21.54±0.76 ^a
	3	18.45±0.63 ^a	18.95±0.59 ^a	20.15±0.41 ^a	18.14±0.65 ^a
	4	15.32±0.39 ^a	15.14±0.94 ^a	17.76±0.50 ^a	17.43±0.61 ^a
	5	14.68±0.61 ^a	14.64±0.83 ^a	16.59±0.41 ^a	15.76±0.65 ^a
VAP (µm/s)	1	43.79±1.07 ^a	43.41±1.62 ^a	43.49±1.59 ^a	38.15±1.83 ^b
	2	36.73±0.63 ^a	36.05±0.86 ^a	36.47±0.86 ^a	35.18±0.59 ^a
	3	30.91±0.68 ^a	32.85±0.45 ^a	32.93±0.36 ^a	30.23±0.97 ^a
	4	26.65±0.69 ^{bc}	26.11±1.04 ^b	30.21±0.45 ^a	30.04±0.58 ^{ac}
	5	24.26±0.95 ^a	25.47±0.84 ^a	27.72±0.58 ^a	25.18±1.00 ^a
BCF (Hz)	1	8.77±0.11 ^a	8.62±0.09 ^a	8.78±0.19 ^a	8.40±0.22 ^a
	2	7.05±0.27 ^{ab}	6.95±0.27 ^{ab}	7.53±0.24 ^a	6.72±0.19 ^b
	3	5.79±0.14 ^a	6.19±0.24 ^a	6.44±0.17 ^a	6.39±0.21 ^a
	4	5.5±0.07 ^b	6.06±0.13 ^{ab}	6.35±0.13 ^a	6.14±0.17 ^{ab}
	5	5.29±0.16 ^b	5.42±0.14 ^{ab}	6.03±0.15 ^a	5.52±0.16 ^{ab}
ALH (µm)	1	1.31±0.03 ^{ab}	1.39±0.02 ^a	1.27±0.04 ^b	1.17±0.05 ^c
	2	1.10±0.01 ^a	1.00±0.02 ^b	1.01±0.03 ^{ab}	1.05±0.01 ^{ab}
	3	0.88±0.02 ^a	0.94±0.03 ^a	0.94±0.02 ^a	0.90±0.03 ^a
	4	0.77±0.01 ^b	0.81±0.03 ^{ab}	0.88±0.01 ^a	0.85±0.02 ^{ab}
	5	0.71±0.02 ^b	0.73±0.03 ^b	0.83±0.02 ^a	0.78±0.03 ^{ab}
STR (%)	1	0.64±0.01 ^a	0.64±0.01 ^a	0.66±0.01 ^a	0.64±0.01 ^a
	2	0.60±0.01 ^a	0.60±0.01 ^a	0.61±0.01 ^a	0.60±0.01 ^a
	3	0.58±0.01 ^a	0.59±0.01 ^a	0.59±0.01 ^a	0.59±0.01 ^a
	4	0.55±0.01 ^a	0.56±0.01 ^a	0.57±0.01 ^a	0.59±0.01 ^a
	5	0.54±0.02 ^b	0.56±0.02 ^{ab}	0.59±0.01 ^a	0.59±0.01 ^a
LIN (%)	1	0.29±0.00 ^a	0.28±0.01 ^a	0.29±0.01 ^a	0.28±0.01 ^a
	2	0.28±0.00 ^a	0.28±0.01 ^a	0.29±0.01 ^a	0.28±0.01 ^a
	3	0.29±0.00 ^a	0.30±0.00 ^a	0.30±0.00 ^a	0.30±0.00 ^a
	4	0.29±0.01 ^a	0.31±0.01 ^a	0.30±0.01 ^a	0.30±0.00 ^a
	5	0.27±0.01 ^a	0.28±0.01 ^a	0.28±0.01 ^a	0.25±0.02 ^a
WOB (%)	1	0.45±0.00 ^a	0.45±0.00 ^a	0.44±0.00 ^a	0.44±0.00 ^a
	2	0.48±0.01 ^b	0.48±0.01 ^b	0.51±0.01 ^a	0.47±0.01 ^b
	3	0.49±0.00 ^a	0.48±0.01 ^{ab}	0.46±0.01 ^b	0.47±0.00 ^{ab}
	4	0.49±0.01 ^a	0.45±0.01 ^b	0.48±0.00 ^a	0.48±0.00 ^a
	5	0.47±0.01 ^a	0.47±0.01 ^a	0.47±0.01 ^a	0.47±0.01 ^a

Table S3

Effects of different concentrations of Mn on sperm motility and other movement parameters in boars.

Kinematic variables	Time (d)	Groups			
		0 µg/mL Mn	0.5 µg/mL Mn	1 µg/mL Mn	2 µg/mL Mn
Motility (%)	1	80.19±0.58 ^a	80.06±0.74 ^a	81.55±0.84 ^a	78.31±0.41 ^a
	2	71.90±0.68 ^a	71.69±0.63 ^a	73.35±0.64 ^a	71.72±0.84 ^a
	3	66.27±0.76 ^a	67.81±1.09 ^a	68.12±1.06 ^a	67.72±0.76 ^a
	4	64.38±0.63 ^a	65.80±0.92 ^a	67.22±0.80 ^a	65.25±1.44 ^a
	5	57.96±1.36 ^a	58.24±0.91 ^a	60.96±1.47 ^a	59.95±0.99 ^a
VCL (µm/s)	1	103.19±3.16 ^{ab}	114.02±4.03 ^a	101.19±7.46 ^{ab}	95.66±2.20 ^b
	2	76.20±1.94 ^a	75.00±2.29 ^a	72.91±2.22 ^a	65.76±1.62 ^a
	3	65.87±1.61 ^a	67.81±1.09 ^a	68.12±1.06 ^a	67.72±0.76 ^a
	4	52.99±0.93 ^b	65.90±2.49 ^{ab}	63.58±3.66 ^{ab}	66.81±2.00 ^a
	5	52.38±6.98 ^a	59.11±6.63 ^a	61.29±7.41 ^a	59.65±5.36 ^a
VSL (µm/s)	1	28.96±0.80 ^a	27.94±1.17 ^a	28.09±0.87 ^a	26.16±1.68 ^a
	2	22.20±0.60 ^a	21.53±0.74 ^a	23.54±0.57 ^a	20.70±0.77 ^a
	3	18.45±0.63 ^b	18.49±0.56 ^b	22.20±0.59 ^a	21.07±0.50 ^{ab}
	4	15.32±0.39 ^b	19.60±0.37 ^a	19.58±0.51 ^a	18.37±0.59 ^a
	5	14.68±0.61 ^a	14.43±1.32 ^a	14.55±0.58 ^a	12.50±1.01 ^a
VAP (µm/s)	1	43.79±1.07 ^b	49.81±2.01 ^a	43.69±2.83 ^b	40.34±0.78 ^b
	2	36.73±0.63 ^b	38.34±1.26 ^{ab}	42.48±1.73 ^a	33.73±0.56 ^b
	3	30.91±0.68 ^a	32.12±0.90 ^a	31.58±1.21 ^a	29.39±1.03 ^a
	4	26.65±0.69 ^a	31.08±1.64 ^a	27.79±1.43 ^a	29.21±1.51 ^a
	5	24.26±0.95 ^a	25.61±0.68 ^a	27.15±0.90 ^a	25.9±0.78 ^a
BCF (Hz)	1	8.77±0.11 ^c	11.34±0.11 ^a	10.28±0.61 ^b	10.84±0.26 ^{ab}
	2	7.05±0.27 ^b	7.72±0.33 ^{ab}	8.34±0.34 ^a	7.82±0.29 ^{ab}
	3	5.79±0.14 ^c	7.60±0.17 ^b	8.26±0.23 ^{ab}	8.78±0.12 ^a
	4	5.50±0.07 ^b	7.66±0.21 ^a	7.82±0.34 ^a	7.79±0.31 ^a
	5	5.29±0.16 ^b	6.01±0.15 ^{ab}	6.13±0.18 ^{ab}	6.36±0.25 ^a
ALH (µm)	1	1.31±0.03 ^a	1.33±0.04 ^a	1.26±0.07 ^{ab}	1.19±0.03 ^b
	2	1.10±0.01 ^a	0.99±0.02 ^{ab}	1.02±0.03 ^{ab}	0.93±0.02 ^b
	3	0.88±0.02 ^b	1.10±0.03 ^a	1.19±0.04 ^a	0.97±0.01 ^b
	4	0.77±0.01 ^b	0.92±0.04 ^a	0.80±0.04 ^b	0.87±0.02 ^{ab}
	5	0.71±0.02 ^b	0.81±0.02 ^{ab}	0.83±0.03 ^a	0.80±0.01 ^{ab}
STR (%)	1	0.64±0.01 ^b	0.72±0.01 ^a	0.71±0.01 ^a	0.72±0.01 ^a
	2	0.60±0.01 ^b	0.66±0.02 ^a	0.65±0.02 ^a	0.66±0.01 ^a
	3	0.58±0.01 ^c	0.68±0.01 ^{ab}	0.66±0.01 ^b	0.71±0.01 ^a
	4	0.55±0.01 ^b	0.68±0.01 ^a	0.69±0.01 ^a	0.69±0.01 ^a
	5	0.54±0.02 ^b	0.65±0.01 ^a	0.66±0.01 ^a	0.67±0.01 ^a
LIN (%)	1	0.29±0.00 ^a	0.31±0.01 ^a	0.31±0.01 ^a	0.30±0.01 ^a
	2	0.28±0.00 ^a	0.29±0.01 ^a	0.27±0.01 ^a	0.28±0.01 ^a
	3	0.29±0.00 ^a	0.31±0.00 ^a	0.29±0.01 ^a	0.31±0.01 ^a
	4	0.29±0.01 ^a	0.30±0.01 ^a	0.31±0.01 ^a	0.29±0.01 ^a
	5	0.27±0.01 ^a	0.28±0.01 ^a	0.29±0.01 ^a	0.29±0.00 ^a
WOB (%)	1	0.45±0.00 ^a	0.44±0.00 ^{ab}	0.44±0.01 ^{ab}	0.42±0.01 ^b
	2	0.48±0.01 ^a	0.44±0.01 ^b	0.42±0.01 ^b	0.42±0.00 ^b
	3	0.49±0.00 ^a	0.45±0.00 ^b	0.44±0.00 ^b	0.44±0.01 ^b
	4	0.49±0.01 ^a	0.44±0.01 ^b	0.44±0.01 ^b	0.42±0.01 ^b
	5	0.47±0.01 ^a	0.43±0.00 ^b	0.45±0.01 ^{ab}	0.44±0.00 ^a

Fig. S1. Characterization and Antioxidant activity of the Mn-ZnO. (A,B) TEM and lattice constant of Mn-ZnO; (C) HAADF and corresponding mapping images of Mn-ZnO; (D-F) XPS of Mn-ZnO; (G) XRD patterns of Mn-ZnO; (H) Zeta Potential of Mn-ZnO.

The morphology of Mn-ZnO was characterized by transmission electron microscopy (TEM), revealing uniformly dispersed nanoparticles (Figure S1A) and characteristic ZnO lattice fringes with a (100) interplanar spacing of 0.28 nm (Figure S1B), indicating unaltered crystal structure following Mn doping. High-angle annular dark-field scanning transmission electron microscopy (HAADF-STEM) imaging and energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX) elemental mapping (Figure S1C) demonstrated homogeneous distribution of Zn and Mn throughout the Mn-ZnO lattice.

The full X-Ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy (XPS) spectrum (Figure S1D) indicated that the Mn-ZnO is mainly composed of three elements: O, Zn, and Mn. The

Zn 2p XPS spectrum (Figure S1E) showed peaks at 1045 eV and 1022eV, confirming that the oxidation state of Zn is +2 in the Mn-ZnO. Similarly, the Mn 2p spectrum (Figure S1F) showed peaks at 641eV and 655.7eV, suggesting that Mn also existed at +2 valence in Mn-ZnO. The above characterizations collectively verify the successful synthesis of Mn-ZnO (Figure S2). The crystal structures of the Mn-ZnO were analyzed by XRD, revealing that both ZnO samples before and after Mn doping had the typical hexagonal fibrillar zincite-type phase [1] (Figure S1G). No additional characteristic peaks attributed to metal Mn or oxide phases appeared in the Mn-ZnO, indicating that Mn doped into the ZnO lattice without changing the ZnO phase structure. The zeta potentials of the ZnO and Mn-ZnO were measured to be +31.03 mV and +32.04 mV, respectively (Figure S1H), and the nanoparticles were positively charged with good dispersibility that can improve the utilization of the particles.

Fig. S2. Synthesis of Mn-ZnO.

Fig. S3. Biosafety assessment of Mn-ZnO. (A) Cytotoxicity assessment of Mn-ZnO in mouse macrophages (RAW264.7) (n = 5); (B) *in vitro* hemolysis assay of Mn-ZnO (n = 3); serum levels of (C) alanine transaminase (ALT), (D) aspartate transaminase (AST), (E) urea (Ur), and (F) creatinine (Cr) between the Mn-ZnO group (10 mg/kg) and the control group on days 1, 6, 12 (n=3); hematological parameters including (G) red blood cell counts (RBC), (H) hemoglobin (HGB), (I) mean red blood cell volume (MCV), (J) white blood cell count (WBC), (K) lymphocyte percentage (Lymph %), and (L) granulocyte percentage (Gran %) between the Mn-ZnO group (10 mg/kg) and the control group on days 1, 6, 12 (n=3); (M) H&E-stained tissue sections of heart, liver, spleen, lungs, and kidneys from the Mn-ZnO group (10 mg/kg) and the control group on day 12 (n=3). “*” indicates P < 0.05 compared with the control control.

To assess the safety profile of Mn-ZnO, we conducted both *in vitro* (using RAW264.7 cells) and *in vivo* (using mice) toxicity evaluations (Fig. S3). Following a seven-day acclimatization period, the mice were randomly divided into two groups: one group received intraperitoneal injections of Mn-ZnO at a dose of 10 mg/kg (0.2 mL per injection) every 2 days for 12 days, while the control group received intraperitoneal injections of saline on the same schedule. The experiment was performed over time points of 1, 6, and 12 days to evaluate potential toxic effects.

At a concentration of 5 µg/mL, Mn-ZnO exhibited no significant effect on macrophage viability *in vitro*, as determined by the CCK-8 assay (Fig. S3A), indicating minimal cytotoxicity and negligible anti-proliferative activity at this dose. The results showed no significant differences in sperm motility between the Mn-ZnO

group and the control group (Fig. S3B). Serum biochemical results indicated no significant differences in liver function parameters (AST and ALT) between the Mn-ZnO group and the control group (Fig. S3C and D). Similarly, there were no significant differences in renal function parameters (Ur) between the Mn-ZnO group and the control group (Fig. S3E), while renal function parameters (Cr) showed a significant difference on day 12 (Fig. S3F), suggesting no liver or kidney damage caused by Mn-ZnO. The results of blood phase analysis (Fig. S3G-L) also showed that there was no significant change in the blood indicators between Mn-ZnO group and the control group. Pathological section analysis (Fig. S3M) further confirmed normal tissue architecture without necrosis, congestion, or hemorrhage in any of the evaluated organs across all groups.

In conclusion, Mn-ZnO at a dose of 10 mg/kg exhibited no proliferative toxicity in RAW264.7 cells and caused no significant toxicity or damage to the physiological health or organ function of mice. No abnormal changes were observed in hematological or biochemical parameters, and H&E staining revealed no abnormalities in organ tissues structures. These results demonstrates that Mn-ZnO is safe for mice and does not significantly impact their physiological state or tissue health, supporting its safety for use.

Reference

[1] Yang L, Yang J, Liu X, Zhang YJ, Wang YX, Fan HG, Wang DD and Lang JH 2008. Low-temperature synthesis and characterization of ZnO quantum dots. *Journal of Alloys and Compounds* 463(1), 92-95.